

Sustainable exploration of orthomagmatic (critical) raw materials in the EU: project SEMACRET

Prospecção de matérias-primas (críticas) de origem ortomagmática na EU: projeto SEMACRET

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Resumo: A disponibilidade de matérias-primas críticas (MPC) relacionadas com depósitos ortomagmáticos (Co-Ni-Cr-PGE-V-Ti) na EU encontra-se presentemente confinada a duas minas na Finlândia, embora outras intrusões (ultra)máficas conhecidas revelem potencial assinalável. O projecto SEMACRET, financiado pelo programa-quadro Horizon Europe, pretende melhorar o conhecimento existente sobre sistemas mineralizados ortomagmáticos e desenvolver métodos de prospecção inovadores e não-invasivos. Adicionalmente, integra investigadores de ciências sociais que irão aferir a perceção dos cidadãos acerca da necessidade/importância da prospecção e exploração mineral, bem como do abastecimento responsável de MPC. A abordagem selecionada baseia-se na caracterização sistémica dos processos mineralizantes, procurando identificar os principais requisitos para formar um depósito mineral: uma fonte de metais (e.g. plumas mantélicas vs. manto continental sub-litosférico), um “caminho” (e.g. descontinuidades trans-litosféricas; condutas à escala da intrusão) e domínios circunscritos no seio da intrusão favoráveis à deposição mineral. Os estudos de caso distribuem-se pela Finlândia, Polónia, República Checa e Portugal (Complexo Ígneo de Beja).

Key words: Sustainable Mineral Exploration, Critical Raw Materials, Orthomagmatic ore-forming systems.

Palavras Chave: Prospecção Mineral sustentável; Matérias Primas Críticas; Mineralizações ortomagmáticas.

The EU defined 30 Critical Raw Materials (CRM) which have both high supply risks and high economic importance. These materials are fundamental to the EU's industrial value chain and strategic sectors, and especially to green energy transition. Among the 30 CRM many are hosted in orthomagmatic sulfide and oxide mineral deposits. These include cobalt, nickel, vanadium, titanium, chromium, copper, and Platinum Group Elements (PGE). Currently, there are two orthomagmatic sulfide deposit in Europe (Kevitsa, Ni-Cu-Co-PGE; Kemi, Cr, Finland), whereas many regions where mafic/ultramafic complexes exist remain underexplored despite several mineral occurrences being reported.

The mineral exploration industry uses a joint approach of geological (including drilling), geophysical, and geochemical methods to delimit mineral resources and assess the economic feasibility of their exploitation. It is therefore desirable that mineral exploration is carried out with the lowest possible expenditure and impact to the environment and populations. Additionally, the low awareness of citizens regarding the need of CRM, their strategic importance to EU and

the shared civilizational responsibility for their sustainable sourcing, represent growing challenges for explorers, scientists, and policy makers. SEMACRET (www.semacret.eu) is a HEU project comprising an international consortium with multi-disciplinary expertise that aims at improving the knowledge on orthomagmatic ore-forming systems and create innovative, responsible exploration methods to find new deposits. Additionally, a group of social scientists will assess citizens awareness on the need of mining and exploration activities to ensure responsible sourcing of raw materials. The project employs the Mineral Systems Approach- MSA which, in a simplified way, acknowledges the formation of mineral deposits as an interplay between a metal source, a pathway and a sink. The application of this knowledge-driven exploration concept to orthomagmatic deposits poses many challenges namely translating the MSA components into (mappable) criteria at a regional (greenfield-Fig. 1) or local scale (brownfield- Fig. 2)

Although the **source** of the targeted deposits is the mantle, the exact origin of the melts (e.g. plume versus Subcontinental Lithospheric Mantle- SCLM) has implications for magma fertility and can be obscured

by subsequent crustal contamination. Conventional litho-geochemistry and isotopic systems such as Re-Os can effectively be used to constrain the source and therefore prospectivity of the magmas. Ni-sulfide deposits form in highly dynamic, magma conduit systems, where magmas can rise quickly and interact with country rock before olivine depletes the melts in Ni.

Fig. 1. Translating the Mineral System Approach to regional (green field) exploration. SCLM- Subcontinental Lithospheric Mantle

The location of the magmas **pathway** in this and other orthomagmatic mineralisation types (PGE, Cr, Ti, V) is relevant to understand the petrogenesis of their host intrusions and can be achieved by multiple techniques. Deep penetration geophysical methods are primarily employed to identify trans-crustal lineaments in the deep crust enabling magma ascent. It is paramount to recognise primitive magma domains using geochemical criteria (high #Mg, high Ni), locating overabundance of cumulates and xenoliths, or use small-scale tracers such as complex zoning in silicates and anomalously slow cooling rates using geothermometric techniques.

Fig. 2. Methods to be employed in local (brown field) exploration.

The **sink** corresponds to limited domains within the intrusions which are increasingly challenging to target. The best deposits occur in intrusions with a long-lasting history of heat flow and magmatic pulses. A particularly valuable tool is the simultaneous study of mineralised and barren intrusions within the same setting/region to understand the critical features that determined (the absence of) ore formation. Additional constraints to refine genetic models will be drawn from numerical modelling of magmatic flow and HT sulfide-melt experiments, whereas surface geochemistry (soil and plants) plus ground and airborne geophysics will be employed to delimit mineralised areas in reference sites. Prospectivity modelling and machine-learning approaches, making use of regional and deposit-scale datasets, will ultimately enable outlining robust exploration vectoring tools to be employed in other settings.

Research will be conducted at five reference sites: Finland (Akanvaara layered intrusion; V-Cr-PGE); Poland (Sleza ophiolite and Suwalki Massive anorthosite; Fe-Ti-V); Czech Republic (Rankso Massif, Ni-Cu-Co-PGE); and Portugal (Beja Igneous Complex) representing different geological, social and environmental conditions. Building upon previous work from IDL/FCUL researchers, SEMACRET will assess the potential for Fe-Ti-V oxides in various areas of the Beja Layered Gabbroic Sequence, as well as the diorite envelope extending to the NW (Cuba Alvito Complex). An heli-transported geophysical campaign (EM, GravMag) will soon be deployed, later followed by ground IP to elucidate the relationship between the non-conformable oxide masses and host gabbros. Using these known areas as training sets, surface geochemistry will be used to identify additional geochemical anomalies. Mineralogical, geochemical, and isotopic studies will monitor chemostratigraphy and redox-sensitive elements to trace fractionation paths whereas a large-scale Nd-Sr-Pb survey will enable to delimit crustal domains of variable crustal contamination. The age and geochemistry of country-rocks will also be investigated to provide precise constraints to modelling crustal contamination. Although olivine chemistry suggests unfavourable conditions for magmatic sulfide generation during LGS main magmatic stage (which may be related either with sulfide removal at depth or shallow flux-melting processes), the potential for magmatic sulfide will also be assessed.

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